

Studies on Interaction between Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) Metal Ions and Substituted Chalcones and Isoxazolines at 0.1M Ionic Strength Potentiometrically and Spectrophotometrically

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The interaction of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3-nitrochalcone (1), 2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl-3-nitrochalcone (2), 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)isoxazoline (3) and 3-(2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)isoxazoline (4) have been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength. The metal ions form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with all the ligands. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by Irving-Rossotti's expression.

Spectrophotometric investigation of the Cu^{II} complexes with substituted chalcone and isoxazoline has shown 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex formation. The spectrophotometric method is compared with potentiometric method. The results obtained of stability constants are in good agreement.

In view of analytical applications of chalcones and isoxazolines, it is of interest to know the physicochemical properties, such as stabilities of the complexes with transition metal ions.

The efficiency of chalcones as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric estimation of a number of metal cations has been studied by Syamsunder¹. Very few complexes of chalcones have been studied potentiometrically. Khadikar *et al.*² studied chelate forming tendency of 2-hydroxy- and 2,4-dihydroxy-chalcone. Narwade and Chincholkar³ studied the stability constant of Fe^{III} chelates with some substituted chalcones at various ionic strengths. Metal chelates of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylisoxazole with several metal ions have been reported⁴. The spectral properties of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylisoxazole have also been reported⁵. Gudadhe *et al.*⁶ studied the physical properties of Th^{IV} complexes of some substituted pyrazolines. Recently, Sawalakhe and Narwade⁷ have studied the interaction between Fe^{III} and Al^{III} metal ions with some substituted diketones. Several workers have studied metal chelates of hydro-dimedone dyes⁸, the stability constants of some lanthanide ions

with sulphonic acid spectrophotometrically⁹, spectrophotometric determination of cyanide in biological sample using new reagent¹⁰, and Fe^{III} complex with some substituted chalcones by spectrophotometric technique¹¹. Hence, it was decided to study the complexes of nitrochalcones and the corresponding isoxazolines potentiometrically and spectrophotometrically.

In the present work, the interactions of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3-nitrochalcone (1), 2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl-3-nitrochalcone (2), 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)isoxazoline (3) and 3-(2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)isoxazoline (4) have been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 0.1M ionic strength. We have also studied the conformation of complex ligands 1-4 with copper metal ion using isobastic point method and Job's variation method.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric measurement :

Proton-ligand stability constants : It is observed

Fig. 1. Plots of vol. of NaOH vs pH for the Cu^{II}-ligand (1) system.

from titration curves that the ligand curves start deviating from the free acid (HClO₄) curves at pH > 7.00. One of the representative graphs of Cu^{II}-ligand (1) system is shown in Fig. 1. The extent of deviation may be the dissociation of OH group completely. The proton-ligand formation numbers ($\bar{n}_A$) were calculated by Irving-Rossotti expression¹². pK values were estimated from formation curves ($\bar{n}_A$ vs pH) by noting pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The accurate values of pK were determined by pointwise calculations. The results reveal that pK values of chalcones are greater than those of isoxazoline. It is also observed (Table 1) that pK values of ligand 1 > 2 and pK values of ligand 3 > 4. This may be due to the fact that nitro group is present as electron-withdrawing group nearer to hydroxyl group in ligand 2 and 4. This leads to reduced pK values.

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Ligand	Constant pK	
	Half-integral	Pointwise
1	10.75	10.78 ± 0.05
2	9.70	9.65 ± 0.04
3	9.10	9.15 ± 0.05
4	9.05	9.10 ± 0.03

Metal-ligand stability constants : The formation of chelates between Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and substituted chalcones and isoxazolines was indicated by the significant departure, starting at pH 6.5 of metal complex titration curves and the change in colour from light brown to dark brown and finally to deep brown as pH changed from 6.5 to 8.5.

In calculating the $\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation number) and pL, the concentration was corrected for change in volume by the addition of alkali during titration. The log K (stability constant) values were directly read from the formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) using half-integral method. The accurate values were calculated by pointwise calculation. It is seen that there is a simultaneously formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

Difference between log K₁ and log K₂ values : The difference between log K₁ and log K₂ values was studied for all the systems and one of the systems is represented in Table 2. It could be seen that log K for ligand 1 > 2, and log K for ligand 3 > 4. This may be due to the effect of electron-withdrawing nitro group nearer to hydroxyl group. One could expect a bigger difference between log K₁ and log K₂ values in such ligand because of possible hindrance to linking of the secondary ligand to the metal ion. The smaller difference may be due to *trans*-structure. The Table 3 shows that

TABLE 2-METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Metal-ligand system	log K ₁	log K ₂	(log K ₁ -log K ₂)	log K ₁ /log K ₂
Cu ^{II} -1	5.49	5.15	0.34	1.06
Cu ^{II} -2	4.69	4.53	0.16	1.03
Cu ^{II} -3	5.09	4.75	0.34	1.07
Cu ^{II} -4	4.70	4.21	0.49	1.11

TABLE 3-CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SUBSTITUTED CHALCONES AND ISOXAZOLINES

Metal-ligand system	K	log K
Cu ^{II} -1	0.10 × 10 ³	2.03
Cu ^{II} -2	0.06 × 10 ³	1.72
Cu ^{II} -3	0.83 × 10 ³	1.92
Cu ^{II} -4	0.06 × 10 ³	1.79

the ratio $\log K_1/\log K_2$ is possible in all cases. Separation factors between first and second formation constants are well within the expected range and the absence of high values implies that there is a little or no steric hindrance to the addition of secondary ligand molecule.

Spectroscopic measurement :

Isobastic point method : It is seen from absorption vs wavelength plot that the curve is intersecting at 515 nm. This indicated the presence of two complex species (i.e. 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes) in the pH range studied. Potentiometric technique also showed the presence of two complex species of Cu^{II} complex with substituted chalcones and isoxazolines.

Job's method : The data of absorption vs percentage composition were used to construct the optical density vs composition curves for all the systems. It was observed that 1 : 1 complex formation occurs at pH 3.0 for the Cu^{II} complexes with all the ligands. The 1 : 1 complex formation was also confirmed at about 3.0 by means of potentiometric technique. Conditional stability constants of metal-ligand complexes were calculated for all the systems (Table 3). It could be seen that conditional stability constants of systems 2 and 4 are lower than those of 1 and 3. It may be due to the presence of nitro group in ligands 2 and 4.

The plots of extension co-efficient against pH at 550 and 580 nm were constructed. It showed that 1 : 1 complex is present in the pH range 3.02–4.0. The $\bar{n}$ values were calculated by the procedure given by McBryde¹⁵ and formation curve were constructed. $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values (first and second metal-ligand stability constants) were obtained by pointwise calcula-

tion method. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ obtained by spectrophotometric and potentiometric measurements are presented in Table 4. It is observed that the values obtained from both the techniques are in good agreement.

Experimental

The ligands 1–4 were synthesised following the reported method and the compounds were crystallised from ethanol before used.

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The ligand solutions were prepared in the purified 1,4-dioxane because they were insoluble in water.

pH measurements were carried with an accuracy ± 0.05 units using glass-calomel electrode. A spectrophotometer was used for measurement of absorption of the solution.

For potentiometric titration (Calvin-Bjerrum) the following carbonate-free solutions were used : (i) free HClO_4 ($1.00 \times 10^{-2}M$), (ii) free HClO_4 ($1.00 \times 10^{-2}M$) + ligand ($20.00 \times 10^{-4}M$) and (iii) free HClO_4 ($1.00 \times 10^{-2}M$) + ligand ($20.00 \times 10^{-4}M$) + metal ion solution ($4.00 \times 10^{-4}M$) against standard solution of sodium hydroxide ($0.108M$). The ionic strength of each solution was maintained constant ($0.1M$) by adding an approximate amount of $1M$ NaClO_4 solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert N_2 -atmosphere.

Vareille's¹⁴ method of isobastic point was used to study the complex formation between Cu^{II} and substituted chalcones and isoxazolines. The absorption was measured for solution containing copper ion ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) and ligand ($100 \times 10^{-4}M$) at pH range 2.0–7.0.

Job's variation method was adopted to know the nature of the complexes. The solution of Cu^{II} ($1 \times 10^{-2}M$) was prepared in 70% dioxane-water mixture and ionic strength maintained constant ($0.1M$) by adding an appropriate amount of $1M$ sodium perchlorate solution. The pH values of each composition were adjusted constant by adding suitable amount of either HCl or NaOH solution. λ_{max} was determined using one of the compositions of which there is maximum absorption. The

TABLE 4—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 0.1 M IONIC STRENGTH

Metal-ligand system	Spectrophotometric		Potentiometric	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Cu^{II} -1	5.40	5.09	5.49	5.15
Cu^{II} -2	4.65	4.49	4.69	4.53
Cu^{II} -3	5.11	4.80	5.09	4.75
Cu^{II} -4	4.75	4.19	4.70	4.21

absorption for all the compositions were recorded at a constant wavelength.

References

1. K. SYAMSUNDR, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1964, **4**, 241.
2. S. N. KHADIKAR and S. N. KAKKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 1319; S. N. KHADIKAR, S. N. KAKKAR and D. D. BURGE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 844; *Indian Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **11**.
3. M. L. NARWADI and M. M. CHINCHOLKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **60**, 194.
4. A. E. MARTELLI and L. G. SILLEN, "Stability Constant of Metal Ion Complexes", Spl. Publ. nos. 17 and 25, Chemical Society, London, 1964 and 1971.
5. S. J. SWAMY and P. LIGAIN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 723.
6. S. GUDHADE, M. L. NARWADE and V. S. JAMODE, *Acta Cinecia Indica*, 1985, **11**, 234.
7. P. D. SAWALAKHE and M. L. NARWADE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, Communicated.
8. A. ATEF and T. RAMDAN, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, **4**, 457.
9. M. L. NARWADE, A. S. WANKHADE and B. G. KHOBRADE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 360.
10. S. SUNITA and V. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 431.
11. M. L. NARWADE, S. W. SATHE and M. M. CHINCHOLKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 194.
12. H. S. IRVING and R. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
13. A. G. DOSHI and B. J. GHIYA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1986, **55**, 502.
14. L. VAREILLE, *Bull. Soc. Fr.*, 1955, **7**, 870.
15. W. A. F. MCBRYDE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 1917.